

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for metabolite profiling of human urine via GC Orbitrap

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Summary

Urinary chemical profiles provide distinct and continuous metabolic phenotypes suited for longitudinal personalised monitoring. Profiling via GC-MS is favourable as it provides robust measures across many core primary metabolic pathways; including amino acids, TCA & urea cycle metabolites, nucleic acids, catecholamines, carbohydrates and some lipids (e.g. steroids & fatty acid). A protocol for simple preparation of urine samples intended to undergo GC-MS analysis is described and enables large-scale semi-quantitative profiling.

Preparation

Safety information

- Urine is classified as a biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.
- All work should be conducted in fume hood.
 - MeOx: Danger - corrosive, harmful, health hazard, environmental hazard
 - Pyridine: Danger - harmful, flammable
 - MSTFA: Warning - harmful, flammable
 - C₇-C₄₀ alkane series (heptane) – flammable, harmful, health hazard, environmental hazard
 - Standard mixes – see below

Equipment

- 10 µL 100 µL & 5 mL pipettes
- Centrifugal evaporator (or N₂ evaporator)
- Storage boxes for 2 mL vials
- Dry heat bath with aluminium blocks for 2 mL vials
- Mini vortex
- Microcentrifuge with rotor for 2 mL vials

Consumables & glassware

- 2 mL screw cap glass autosampler vials with built-in 200 µL insert and caps (PTFE septa)

- 10 μ L , 100 μ L & 5 mL tips
- Labels for 2 mL vials
- 10 – 20 mL glass tube with tight sealing screw cap

Reagents

- Urine normalised to specific gravity of 1.0020 and kept on ice
- Fresh milliQ water
 - Alternatively, can use purchased LC-MS grade water within one-two weeks of opening bottle
- GC grade anhydrous pyridine >99% purity
 - Pyridine will discolour to yellow if old or impure.
- C₇-C₄₀ alkane series mix (saturated 1000 μ g/mL in heptane)
- Methoxyamine hydrochloride (MeOx) > 97.5%
 - MeOx reacts with carbonyl groups (e.g. ketones, aldehydes) to form oxime and prevent numerous enol forms that gives rise to many peaks, especially for reducing sugars.
- *N*-methyl-*N*-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) > 98%
 - MSTFA replaces free hydroxyl groups with trimethylsilyl (TMS) to reduce polarity and increase volatility (alcohol > phenol > carboxylic acid > amine > amide).
 - Alternatively can use MSTFA + 1% trimethylchlorosilane (TMCS) as an extra catalyst if many sites observed to be unreacted. (Typically, does not make a difference when using pyridine).

MeOx solution (20 mg/mL in pyridine)

- For 5 mL of solution, weigh 100 mg methoxyamine hydrochloride into glass tube.
- Add 5 mL of pyridine and vortex until dissolved.
 - Solution can be kept for 3 days at room temp. Store double wrapped (e.g. parafilm cap and place glass tube in plastic falcon).

Standards (optional but recommended)

Standard mix 1 (10 μ g/mL each)

D3-Levodopa – harmful

D3-L-Leucine

D4-Putrescine dihydrochloride – harmful

D4-Succinic acid – corrosive, harmful

D6-myo-Inositol

Standard mix 2 (10 μ g/mL each)

D4-4-Nonylphenol – corrosive, harmful, health hazard, environmental hazard

D5-Cholic acid - harmful

D15-Octanoic acid – corrosive

D27-Myristic acid - harmful

Procedure

Sample preparation

1. Working on ice, pipette 10 μL urine sample into 2 mL autosampler vials.
2. For every 10 urine samples, pipette 10 μL water into a 2 mL autosampler vial to act as blank.
3. If using, add 10 μL of standard mix 1 and 10 μL of standard mix 2.
4. Dry samples until complete dryness using a centrifugal evaporator (or under N_2).
 - If using a centrifugal evaporator dry with lamp off and no heat, approximately 1h.
 - If using N_2 it is preferable to “over-dry” as visible dryness is inaccurate.
 - If not possible to dry right away, store samples at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for up to 24h.
5. Store dry samples at $-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ prior to subsequent analysis.

Sample derivatisation

6. Remove samples from freezer, decap and leave for 20 minutes in fume hood.
 - Moisture prevents derivatisation reaction.
7. Pre-heat dry heat block to $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.
8. Add 30 μL of MeOx solution to all samples
9. For each batch of samples include 2 derivatisation blanks, adding 30 μL of MeOx solution into autosampler vial without sample.
 - These blanks are additional to the milliQ blanks prepared with the samples.
10. Incubate samples at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h.
11. Add 70 μL MSTFA and incubate at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h.
12. Remove from heat block & place on ice for a couple of minutes.
13. Vortex and centrifuge samples at 15,000 g for 5 min.
14. In the meantime, prepare solvent blanks by pipetting 50 μL pyridine into 2 mL vials.
 - Prepare a solvent blank for every 8 samples in the batch.
15. Additionally, prepare 50 μL of 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of $\text{C}_7\text{-C}_{40}$ alkane series in pyridine in a 2 mL vial.
16. Pipette 100 μL of each sample into a fresh 2 mL vial and cap.
17. Inject onto GC-MS system.
 - Derivatives should be injected within 24h. At most, derivatives can be injected within 48h if stored free from moisture at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.
 - If required, replace vials caps prior to re-injection of sample.

GC-MS analysis

18. Replace liner and septa per each batch (~50-100 samples)
19. Calibrate and tune MS
20. Input sequence
21. Start GC-MS analysis run

22. Check initial blanks, alkane series and QC samples.

- If problems, stop run, wrap samples in parafilm and store at -20 °C whilst troubleshooting.
- Can do initial checks of blanks / alkane series prior to derivatisation if samples are precious.

GC sequence setup

1. Pyridine blank
2. Alkane series
3. Pyridine blank
4. Derivatisation blank
5. (QC samples xxx)
6. Samples 1-10
7. Pyridine blank
8. Derivatisation blank
9. (QC samples)
10. Samples 11-20
11. Pyridine blank
12. Derivatisation blank
13. (QC samples)
14. Samples 21-30
15. End with 3x pyridine blanks

GC-MS method setup

Autosampler settings

TriPlus RSH Autosampler		Comments
General		
Injection port		
Injector	Injector A (SSL)	
Type	Single	
Injection mode		
Mode	Basic	
Rapid mode		
Rapid mode	Disable	
Syringe type		
Syringe volume (µL)	10	
Needle length (mm)	57	
Sampling		
Sample volume (µL)	2	*Set in method sequence to be 1 µL*
Plunger strokes	0	
Air and filling mode	Custom	
Air volume (µL)	0	
Filling volume (µL)	0	
Sampling depth in vials		
Sample vial depth (mm)	\	
Bottom sense	Yes	
Height from bottom (mm)	1.5	
Injection		
Injection depth	Custom	
Pre-injection dwell time (s)	0	
Post-injection dwell time (s)	0.1	
Fast injection	Off	
Injection depth (mm)	45	
Penetration speed (mm/s)	90	
Injection Speed (µL/s)	50.0	
Sample viscosity		
Sample type	Custom	
Sample pullup speed (µL/s)	0.4	
Delay after plunger strokes (s)	1.5	
Viscosity delay (s)	2.0	
Washes		
Washes		Solvent A: nonane
Number of solvents(s)		Solvent B: toluene
Wash station		Solvent C: acetone
Standard wash station		Solvent D: nonane

Pre-injection		E position: waste			
Solvent	A	\	\	\	
Cycles			4		
Solvent volume (µL)			7.0		
Rinse					
Rinses			0		
Rinse Volume (UI)			1		
Post-injection					
Solvent	\	B	C	D	
Cycles			7		
Solvent volume (µL)			7.0		
Sync					
GC synchro start					
Synchro type			Standard		
Advanced					
Advanced parameters					
Wash solvent depth (mm)			45		
Waste depth (mm)			10		
Needle speed in vial (mm/s)			10		
Solvent filling speed (µL/s)			1		
Bubble elimin. pullup (µL/s)			5		
Delay between strokes (s)			2.0		

GC settings

TRACE 1310 Series GC

Oven

Ramps

	Rate (°C/min)	Temp (°C)	Hold time (min)
Initial		80	0.5
1	40	200	0.5
2	40	260	0.5
3	55	330	4.0

Options

Max temp.	340 °C
Prep-run timeout	10 min
Equilibration time	1 min
Ready delay	0.00 min
Oven on	Yes

Comments

Trace 1310
Column: Rxi-5SiIMS (15m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm) with 2m guard (0.25 mm) at transfer & 2m guard (0.53 mm) at inlet.

S/SL (front)

S/SL mode Splitless w/Surge

Inlet

Temp On 290 °C
 Split flow On 50.0 mL/min
 Split ratio \
 Splitless time 0.80 min

Surge

Surge pressure 140.00 kPA
 Surge duration 0.80 min

Septum purge

Purge flow 3.0 mL/min
 Constant septum purge Yes
 Stop purge for \
 Carrier mode Constant flow

Carrier flow

Flow On 1.2 mL/min

Carrier options

Vacuum compensation On
 Carrier gas saver On
 Gas saver flow 15.0 mL/min
 Gas saver time 3.00 min

Aux. Temperatures

Auxilliary temperature control

Transfer Line 1 On 280 °C
 Transfer Line 2 On 280 °C

Septa: Merlin microseal
 Liner: Restek Topaz 4.0mm precision
 liner w/ wool

MS settings

Q Exactive GC-Orbitrap MS

Global Settings

User role Advanced
 Use lock masses off
 Lock mass injection \
 Time

Method duration 11.5 min
 Customized Tolerances (+/-)

Lock Masses \
 Inclusion \
 Exclusion — \
 Comments

Mass Tags	—	\
Dynamic Exclusion		\
EI/CI Source		
Filament on delay		2.00 min
MS transfer line temp		250 °C
Ion source temp		280 °C
Ionization mode		EI
CI gas type		None
CI gas flow		0.00 mL/min
Use tune emission current		TRUE
Emission current		50.0 µA
Use tune electron energy		FALSE
Electron energy		70 eV
Use tune file C-Trap energy offset		TRUE
C-Trap energy offset		0.0 V
Cal gas level		Off
Properties of Full MS-SIM		
Experiment		Full MS — SIM
General		
Runtime		2 to 11.5 min
Polarity		Positive
Full MS		
Microscans		1
Resolution		60,000
AGC target		1.00E+06
Maximum IT		auto
Scan range		70 to 700 m/z
Spectrum data type		Profile
Setup		
Tunefiles		
General		
Switch Count	0	
Base Tunefile	C:\Xcalibur\methods\EI_20200605_EP-IT50_250_280.mstune	
Tune scan range		70-700
Res		60,000
AGC		1.00E+06
Max inject		50
MS transfer		250
Ion source		280

Update each acquisition - Tune to TIC